

Take me for a ride: herbivores can facilitate plant re-invasions

Lauren L. Sullivan, Allison K. Shaw

Journal: Ecology

Appendix S1

Figure S1: Herbivore syndromes with single effects using a laplace dispersal kernel. Plant population spread speed as a function of increasing herbivore pressure for scenarios [1], [2], and [3]. In each of these scenarios the presence of herbivores (simulated as dots, analytic as solid line) slows population spread compared to the baseline scenario of no herbivores (dashed line) and increasing herbivore pressure (moving right along the x-axis) always decreases spread.

Figure S2: Herbivore syndromes with double effects using a laplace dispersal kernel. Plant population spread speed as a function of increasing herbivore pressure for scenarios [4], [5], [6], and [7]. Here herbivores affect both plant demography (bottom x-axis in each panel) and plant dispersal (top x-axes). In scenarios [4], [5], and [6], the presence of herbivores (simulated as dots, analytic as solid line) can increase population spread compared to the baseline scenario of no herbivores (dashed line) for small herbivore pressure. However, for large herbivore pressure, increasing herbivore pressure decreases spread below the baseline scenario.